

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B280
Date: 29 March 2007
Take Off 12:00:47
Landing: 17:07:41
Flight Time 5h06m54

Campaign: IASI – Test Flight

Operating Area: North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Richard Cotton	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	CCM2 / Core Chem	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
8	Video System	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	TDLAS	Iq Mead	University of Cambridge
10	SAW	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
11	Mission 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
12	MARSS / DEIMOS / Wet Neph	James Bowles	Met Office
13	Wet Neph training	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
14	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
15	AMS1	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
16	AMS2	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B280 Track 29-MAR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b280
 Date: 29/03/2007
 Project: IASI
 Location: N. Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
105736		Start-Up	0.39 kft	128	52'04.36N 0'37.48W
115421		ASP Open	0.40 kft	174	
120047		T/O	0.0 kft	304	
120047	120927	Profile 1	0.0 - 10.0 kft	300	start on T/O
120949	121254	Profile 2	10.1 - 13.0 kft	080	
122234	123737	Profile 3	13.0 - 1.5 kft	057	QNH 1009
123737	125648	Run 1	1.5 kft	054	
124258		turn	1.5 kft	011	turn at point 84
125648	125758	Profile 4	1.4 - 1.1 kft	018	QNH 1009
125758	135606	Run 2	1.1 - 1.0 kft	018	1000ft QH1009 to 50ft
131545		QH	1.1 kft	349	QH 1011
133134		Video	1.1 kft	345	tape changes
133649		QNH	1.1 kft	345	QNH 1012
134150		QNH	1.1 kft	345	QNH 1013
135606	135804	Profile 5	1.0 - 0.00 kft	350	drop to 50ft
135804	143106	profile 6	0.00 - 30.0 kft	350	
141304		Profile 6	15.0 kft	350	interrupt
141521		Profile 6	15.0 kft	166	resume
140112		QNH	2.8 kft	338	QNH 1013
141338		Video	15.0 kft	288	FFC to RFC
143106		Video	30.0 kft	166	RFC to UFC
143419	144420	Run 3.1	30.1 - 30.0 kft	050	down sun
144531	145034	Run 3.2	30.0 kft	326	cross sun azi. 229
145153	150123	Run 3.3	30.1 - 30.0 kft	233	into sun azi. 230
150236	150733	Run 3.4	30.1 - 30.0 kft	146	across sun
150521		Video	30.0 kft	141	new tapes
150857	151114	Profile 7	30.1 - 32.0 kft	058	
151115	152114	Run 4.1	32.0 kft	053	down sun
152227	152728	Run 4.2	32.0 kft	329	cross sun
152845	153845	Run 4.3	32.0 kft	240	into sun
154002	154504	Run 4.4	32.0 kft	152	cross sun
154505	155733	Profile 8	32.0 - 20.1 kft	150	
154534		Video	31.7 kft	141	UFC to RFC
155734	161208	Profile 9	20.1 - 32.0 kft	139	
161208	161638	Run 5.1	32.0 kft	162	cruise power
161638	162037	Run 5.2	32.0 kft	164	int/high power
162037	162505	Run 5.3	32.0 kft	164	full power
162506	162913	Run 5.4	32.0 kft	174	cruise power
162914	163505	Run 5.5	32.0 kft	195	below cruise power
163519	163637	Run 5.6	32.0 - 29.7 kft	228	cruise power
163610		Video	30.9 kft	231	change
170741		Land	0.43 kft	257	
171150		ASP	0.43 kft	309	ASP closed
171152		Shutdown	0.43 kft	309	52'04.36N 0'37.48W

B280 Track 29-MAR-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

IASI INSTRUMENT TEST and VISURB-UK

Flight No: B280

Date: 29th March 2007

Trial objectives:

IASI related Instrument shakedown and training.

To carry out in-situ sampling of aerosol properties and their effect on visibility.

Location:

Over ocean areas downwind of major pollution sources.:North sea.

Areas DELTA and ECHO (for the box pattern and onwards area ECHO).

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric aerosols. Clear skies preferred, but not essential.

Special requirements:

VISURB requires very long low level boundary layer run.

Check the mesoscale model forecast for the position of aerosol plumes before flying.

http://www-nwp/~meso/current_uk4mesglob_charts.html

Instruments of particular importance for VISURB:

Nephelometer/Wet-nephelometer,AMS,PCASP,PSAP,BBRs.

IASI INSTRUMENT TESTS requires deep profiles and high altitude runs.

Cloud-physics tests require some cloud sampling, preferably low level high concentrations.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 13:00L.
2. Transit to operating area and then perform a profile descent from FL100 to 50ft [30mins].
3. Perform SLR in a northerly direction at altitude to be determined by the mission scientist (suggest 500ft) Run length ideally 300miles. Slight changes in heading permissible. [75mins].
4. Profile ascent from 50ft to FL300,interrupting the profile to stay in the same general air-mass. [30mins].
5. Perform a run in a southerly direction at FL300.Changes in heading are permissible.[15mins].
6. Perform a rectangular box pattern, with two short 5 minute legs and two longer 10 minute legs. The long legs are orientated into and away from the sun (SW) This must be in clear air with clear sky above.[40mins].
7. Profile descend to FL150 and then profile ascend to FL300 [30mins].[4 hours total so far]
8. Search for low level cloud for cloud-physics testing. This can be part of the transit back to Cranfield. [60min].
9. Land Cranfield. At 18:00L.

SORTIE DEBRIEF

IASI test flight/VISURB.

Flight number **B280**

29 March 2007

General weather

Operate in the North sea, areas Delta and Echo. Surface chart 12Z shows low pressure region over North sea, with a waving-front down the east coast. To the south, the cold front is slowly moving east, while to the north the warm front is slowly moving west. Early on, there was low level cloud in the south near the coast, and high level cloud in the north which was clearing westwards.

Sortie

Cloud microphysics tests

Sample warm cloud for high droplet concentration tests during climb out.

1. Take-off from Cranfield 12:01:39Z. 8/8 clow cloud with drizzle.
2. Profile ascent **P1** from take-off to FL100 (12:01:39 to 12:09:27). Generally in cloud, with cloud base 1880 ft (rad-alt). Above 6200 ft, messy mid-level cloud.
3. Profile ascent **P2** from FL100 to FL130 (12:09:49 to 12:12:54). Cloud top FL120.
4. Transit at FL130 in clear air. T=-17C. Generally clear skies above with some patchy cirrus and contrails.

VISURB physics

A long 300mile run at 1000 ft with profiles at the start and end.

1. Profile descent **P3** from FL130 to 1400 ft (12:22:34 to 12:37:37). Enter cloud top FL096, T=-11C. Descent delayed at 2000 ft until visibility improves/clear of surface rigs. Still in cloud.
2. Run **R1** at 1400 ft (12:38:21 to 12:56:48). Start run in cloud which gradually changed into a very low visibility airmass. Cloud base reported to be 350 ft. Towards end of run, sea surface visible below but still very low visibility ahead with no clear horizon. Safety altitude is 1000 ft. Cloud physics only sees aerosol (12:52:00).
3. At point 84, profile descent **P4** from 1400 ft to 1000 ft (1009 QNH) (12:57:17 to 12:57:58). Very low visibility determined safety altitude 1000 ft.
4. Run **R2** at 1000 ft (12:57:58 to 13:56:06). For all of this run the visibility was very low, and only aerosols were seen with cloud physics. The sea surface was visible looking down through the side windows but not ahead. There was no clear horizon. Above, generally the sky was clear. Cloud physics ~ 2000 aerosols, no cloud droplets (12:57:54). During this run the altitude was adjusted as the QNH pressure changed. QNH 1011 (12:12:25), QNH 1012 (13:02:30), QNH 1013 (13:42:06). Less convective cloud observed above as QNH increases. The humidity at 1000 ft not high, but increased slightly as the run progressed. T=10C and Tdew=-2C (13:20:00) to T=6C and Tdew=3C (13:42:06). Is sea mist below 1000 ft the cause of the limited visibility?
5. Profile **P5** from 1000 ft to 50 ft (13:56:06 to 13:58:04) at point B.
6. Profile **P6** from 50 ft to FL300 (13:58:04 to 14:31:06) interrupting to turn on reciprocal at FL150. High pollution observed visually below ~ 6000 ft. Some isolated low-level cloud below (1/8) but looks much clearer to east. Clear sky above. Contrails noted (14:29:10) at T=-49C and Tfrost=-53C.

IASI tests

Two rectangular box patterns (Runs R3.* and R4.* at FL300 and FL320) with the long runs into/away from the sun for SWS, box pattern for ARIES.

1. Run **R3.1** at FL300 away from sun azimuth (224) (14:34:19 to 14:44:20). Clear sky above, generally clear below (1/8). T=-52C and Tfrost=-62C.
2. Run **R3.2** at FL300 across sun (14:45:31 to 14:50:34).
3. Run **R3.3** at FL300 into sun azimuth (230) (14:51:53 to 15:01:23). T=-52C and Tfrost=-58C.
4. Run **R3.4** at FL300 across sun (15:02:36 to 15:07:33). From cockpit, no one direction looks clearer than this, so stay in area and repeat box pattern at higher altitude.
5. Profile **P7** from FL300 to FL320.
6. Run **R4.1** at FL320 away from sun azimuth (233) (15:11:15 to 15:21:14). Clear sky above, generally clear below (4/8). T=-55C and Tfrost=-62C. Turbulence.
7. Run **R4.2** at FL320 across sun (15:22:27 to 15:27:28). Clearly see the moon, but the air is hazy with an indistinct horizon (the Earth not the Moon).
8. Run **R4.3** at FL320 into sun azimuth (239) (15:28:45 to 15:38:45). T=-56C and Tfrost=-63C.
9. Run **R4.4** at FL320 across sun (15:40:02 to 15:45:04).

Contrailing for all run R4.* (must check tape for R3.*). FWVS reports slow response to the first profile, so the second profile will be for contrail validation instead.

Contrail validation

During the earlier profiles, contrails were first observed at ~ FL300. Contrail validation tests were attempted during the transit home (at science speed). The engine power was varied and for each setting a 4 minute (allowing humidity stabilisation) run observed contrail formation. The rear facing camera is now being recorded.

1. Profile **P8** from FL320 to FL200 (15:45:05 to 15:57:33). Contrails dissipate between ~ FL295 and ~ FL300. The engine power is being adjusted during the profile descent to keep the rate constant!
2. Profile **P9** from FL200 to FL320 (15:57:34 to 16:12:08). Contrails just form at ~ FL320. Engine power settings are being adjusted.
3. Run **R5.1** at FL320 on normal cruise power (timing needed).
4. Run **R5.2** at FL320 on intermediate to high power (timing needed).
5. Run **R5.3** at FL320 on full power (16:21:55 to 16:25:05).
6. Run **R5.4** at FL320 on normal cruise power (16:25:06 to 16:29:13).
7. Run **R5.5** at FL320 on low power (16:29:14 to 16:35:05).
8. Run **R5.6** at FL320 descending to FL297 on normal cruise power. ATC interrupt further contrail runs. The ambient humidity was changing slightly during these runs.

Mission Scientist's Log

IASI TEST / VISURE.

Flight No **B.280** Date **29 MAR 07** Name **R COTTON** Page **1** of **.....**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					8/8 low - cloud, drizzle.
					Take-off Cranfield.
	P1				P1 started at Take-off.
					In cloud 1880 RAO out
		6200			Cloud top, in/out cloud.
	P1 end				Meag mid level cloud.
120949	P2 start	FL100			T: -13°C still in cloud recommence profile
121254	P2 end	FL130	T: -17°C		out of cloud FL120 clear above
					Some patchy cirrus ahead.
		Transitioning FL130			Contrails above us. 9/8Sc below
	P3 start	FL130		descent	
				FL06	enter cloud turbulence T: -11°C
				2000 ft.	still in cloud. no cloud base, so can not descend
122737	P2 end.	1400ft		9000ft	beyond 1300ft, until clear of rgs.
	P1 start				start run in cloud, then just above Sc. for lot of run.
125200					no cloud physics ice only needed. Cannot get below cloud base still. 9/8Sc
125500	sea surface vis.				safety alt 1000 ft. Now reported 3500.
125648	R1 end.				can see surface thro haze.
	P4 start				S. descent to 1000 ft.
	P4 end			1000ft	lost 9th Limit VIS recommence 20 min - alt
125754	R2 start				~ 2000 aerod. no depts. conc. 20
					Very limited VIS
					See sea surface out of side windows

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.480** Date **1951/11/16** Name **R. (OTN)** Page **2** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	
121225	adjust height	to 1000 ft	QNH	1011	Still low low vis, cannot descend. due to high humidity. Not cloud.	
132000		$T = 10^{\circ}C$	$T_{dew} = -2^{\circ}C$		patchy cirrus above.	
				SAT com message at 1310Z	{ 13Z 55N-57N (cirrus) } moving in NW's dir SE-W also above 58N and 36-1W looks much clearer to East *So clear below 57 and 59N*	
130230	adjust	QNH	1012	at 1000 ft.		$T = 7^{\circ}C$ $T_d = 1^{\circ}C$ Still very limited vis.
		Reasonably dry	so low	vis layer :- below us - sea mist.		
134206	adjust	QNH	1013	at 1000 ft	$T = 5.6^{\circ}C$ $T_d = 3^{\circ}C$ Less convective cloud as QNH increased. High alt, max. Aerial (20) constant 1320-1375	
134700		57°18'N 1°48'E	0/8 Ci	above	Horizon not vis for while now! (will descend to 50 ft to that ^{deep} profile.)	
57°48'N } 1°36'E }	still	at 1000 ft		135500	much less convective cloud, but still very low vis. $T = 7^{\circ}C$ $T_d = -2^{\circ}C$	
135606		R2 end				
135606		P5 start		58°0'N 1°20'E	still 0/8 Ci.	
175806		P5 end			but looks less hazy to East.	
		P6 start		58°18'N, 1°12'E	still 0/8 Ci	
					High pollution below FL060	
		1/8 Cu	below	the	more extensive low cloud towards SW then NW	

Contacts noted during end of profile.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.280**.....

Date **29 MAR 07**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					much clearer to E > 2.
5244	142	910		*	'Contrailing' T: -49°C Td: -53°C
143104	P6 two	FL300			clear above
					224001 AZIMUTH
143419	R3 start	FL300			First Run into sun. (down 'sun')
1436			moon at lock		Generally clear below. To south there is more low-level cloud.
144100					Azimuth now 226-05
144419	R3 end	FL300			T: -52°C Td: -62°C
144530	R4 2 start				Cross-sun run
					* Time is looking good so lets do another box at FL320 *
145040	R2 2 end				
145150	R3 3 start		still no cloud above		Sometimes some Sc/Es below.
				10+com	{ main Ci is SSN - SSN } 20 to 2-56.
150122	R3 3 end	FL300		T: -52	stay to north and East?
150235	R3 4 start			Td: -58°C	still clear above though, so repeat this box pattern, only 2000ft higher.
150730	R3 4 end	FL300			Danger area and airway constraints as from cockpit no one direction looks any better or worse.
15	P7 start P8 end	FL300 FL320			
151122	R4 1 start	FL320		T: -55 Td: -60	4/8 low cloud. down sun run
					Az 233° for R4.1
					We are going to close NE to Norwegian airspace as possible
					NOT good vis.
	R4.2	134 210	turbulence	231	

R4.1
R4.2

clearer to see this side of R3.4.

P6 start
R3.4

230
R3.1

R4.2

224 Az

relate

for vertical box

that why don't want to

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 280

Date: 29/03/2007	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:00:10																Start profile 1 from Takeoff	
12:06:04	210	0.09	141	1												FL070	
12:07:04	110	0.09		1												FL090	
12:08:20	190	0.09	143			25	800	4000	2000						8	End of Profile 1 @ FL100	
12:09:50																Start Profile 2 from FL100	
12:10:54	210	0.09	150	100		6	800	275	800							FL110	
12:12:20	150	0.08														FL120	
12:12:57	150	0.08														End of Profile 2 @ FL130	
12:22:33	60	0.08		1												Start Profile 3 from FL130	
12:23:50	120	0.08		1												FL120	
12:24:50	200	0.08		10												FL110	
12:25:51	530	0.08		1000		4		390								FL100	
12:26:49	580	0.10	153	100		2	300	700							1	FL090	
12:27:43	880	0.10		10		1	300	400							1	FL080	
12:28:48	900	0.10		5												FL070	
12:29:39	890	0.10		3												FL060	
12:30:55	1200	0.10		3												FL050	
12:32:30	1200	0.10		3												FL040	
12:34:42	1200	0.10	154	3												FL030	
12:36:27	2900	0.10		15												FL020	
12:37:40																End of Profile 3 @ 1400' & Start Run 1	
12:38:00	2800	0.10	290	100													
12:40:00	3200	0.11	291	10													
12:42:00	2700	0.11		10													
12:44:00	2100	0.10		10													
12:46:00	2000	0.10		10													
12:48:00	1600	0.11		10													
12:50:00	1100	0.10		10													
12:52:00	1400	0.10		5													
12:54:00	1700	0.10		5													
12:56:00	1900	0.11		5													
12:56:50																End of Run 1 & Start of Profile 4	
12:58:01																End of Profile 4 & Start Run 2 @ 1000'	
12:59:00	2240	0.10	292	5													
13:01:00	2100	0.10		5													
13:03:00	2200	0.10		10													
13:05:00	2400	0.10		10													
13:07:00	2400	0.10	293	10													
13:09:00	2300	0.10		5													
13:11:00	1900	0.10		5													
13:13:00	1700	0.10		5													
13:15:00	1900	0.10		5													
13:17:00	1900	0.10		5													
13:19:00	1900	0.09		5													
13:21:00	1900	0.09	303	5												Jump in FFSSP due to Sig level experiment	
13:23:00	2100	0.10		5													

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 280

Date: 29/03/2007	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:25:00	2100	0.10	303	5													
13:27:00	2400	0.10	304	5													
13:29:00	2600	0.10		10													
13:31:00	2550	0.10		10													
13:33:00	2300	0.10		10													
13:35:00	2600	0.10		10													
13:37:00	2600	0.10	305	10													
13:39:00	2800	0.10		15													
13:41:00	2600	0.10		10													
13:43:00	2600	0.10	306	10													
13:45:00	2550	0.10		10													
13:47:00	2500	0.10		10													
13:49:00	2550	0.10		10													
13:51:00	2550	0.10		10													
13:53:00	2500	0.10		10													
13:56:08																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 4 from 1000'	
13:58:06	2500	0.10	308	100												End of Profile 4 & start Profile 5 from 50'	
13:59:26	1800	0.10	309	10												FL010	
14:00:25	1900	0.10		10												FL020	
14:01:24	1650	0.10		10												FL030	
14:02:30	1530	0.10		10												FL040	
14:03:22	1190	0.10		10												FL050	
14:04:30	1040	0.10		10												FL060	
14:05:30	110	0.10		1												FL070	
14:06:36	55	0.06		1												FL080	
14:07:27	55	0.07		1												FL090	
14:08:22	55	0.07		1												FL100	
14:09:21	50	0.07		1												FL110	
14:10:17	50	0.07		1												FL120	
14:11:15	50	0.07		1												FL130	
14:12:10	60	0.07		1												FL140	
14:13:02	55	0.06		1												FL150	
14:16:43	55	0.06		1												FL160	
14:17:46	80	0.06		1												FL170	
14:18:50	60	0.06		1												FL180	
14:19:45	55	0.06		1												FL190	
14:20:50	50	0.06		1												FL200	
14:21:00	70	0.06		1												FL210	
14:22:51	90	0.06		1												FL220	
14:23:55	110	0.06		1												FL230	
14:24:51	80	0.06		1												FL240	
14:25:47	80	0.06		1												FL250	
14:26:55	110	0.08		1												FL260	
14:27:47	90	0.08		1												FL270	
14:28:55	100	0.08		1				Noise								FL280	
14:29:57	80	0.08		1				Noise								FL290	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 280

Date: 29/03/2007	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:31:08	85	0.08	310					Noise								End of Profile 5 @ FL300	
14:34:21																Start Run 3.1 @ FL300	
14:35:00	140	0.08						Noise									
14:37:00	120	0.08						Noise									
14:39:00	Noise							Noise									
14:41:00	Noise							Noise									
14:43:00	Noise							Noise									
14:44:21																End of Run 3.1	
14:45:38																Start Run 3.2 @ FL300	
14:46:00	Noise							Noise									
14:48:00	Noise							Noise									
14:50:00	Noise							Noise									
14:50:37																End of Run 3.2	
14:51:56																Start Run 3.3 @ FL300	
14:52:00	Noise							Noise									
14:54:00	Noise							Noise									
14:56:00	Noise							Noise									
14:58:00	Noise							Noise									
15:00:00	Noise							Noise									
15:01:28																End of Run 3.3	
15:02:40																Start Run 3.4 @ FL300	
15:03:00	Noise		311					Noise									
15:05:00	Noise							Noise									
15:07:00	Noise							Noise									
15:07:33																End of Run 3.4	
15:08:58																Start Profile 6 from FL300	
15:11:16																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 4.1 @ FL320	
15:12:00	Noise							Noise									
15:14:00	Noise							Noise								59200/54976 63350/50642	
15:16:00	Noise							Noise								8 & 4 -13MB @ -55	
15:18:00	Noise							Noise									
15:20:00	Noise							Noise									
15:21:16																End of Run 4.1	
15:22:35																Start Run 4.2 @ FL320	
15:23:00	Noise							Noise									
15:25:00	Noise							Noise								59200/54976 63350/50640	
15:27:00	Noise							Noise								8 & A -15MB @ -55	
15:27:30																End of Run 4.2	
15:28:45																Start Run 4.3 @ FL320	
15:29:00	Noise							Noise									
15:31:00	Noise							Noise									
15:33:00	Noise							Noise									
15:35:00	Noise							Noise									
15:37:00	Noise							Noise									
15:38:48																End of Run 4.3	
15:40:05																Start Run 4.4 @ FL320	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B280****Date:****29/03/2007**

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B280_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B280_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B280 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B280_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown		Problems running this but Manually edited o/p file
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B280 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use, in order of preference, - if a calibration exists after the flight date, then the file that is closest in time to it, - or the most recent calibration file prior to the flight date. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Note the calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B280_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B280_mfdX','pmsdata:B280_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit		Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B280_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B280_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B280****Date:****29/03/2007**

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B280.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B280.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	17/04/07	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B280.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B280.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B280_seadas.dat iii) exit	17/04/07	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written 52092 blocks read/written No bad blocks
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B280 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B280_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data N j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: N l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	17/04/07	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files. Not required Not required Data ends about 170800
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B280 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)
Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image		

a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B280 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	0 170800 10	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B280_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	18/04/07	Files in O:/CloudPhysics Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end.
a) Flight number: B280 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B280_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B280_PROC2D	120200 171000 0.2 8/8 2 18/04/07	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B280_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B280_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	18/04/07	
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B280_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B280_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	18/04/07	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?	Seems OK	In non-noisy periods

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B280**Date:**

29/03/2007

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures B280_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: B280 b) File name: PMSDATA:B280_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:B280_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:B280_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:B280_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	1 1.25 0 120200 171000	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate From operator log Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
3) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B280_procpcasp.dat' , 'pmsdata:B280_m5procpcasp' iii) exit	18/04/07	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B280_m5procpcasp b) Datset: mfddata:B280_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	MFDB 18/04/07	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B280**Date:**

29/03/2007

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		Defaults in [square brackets]
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:B280_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B280.nc]	18/04/07	As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B280.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B280.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B280_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary	18/04/07	complete

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:B280*.* outdir:B280_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.	18/04/07	Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B280**Date:**

29/03/2007

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC B280_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B280_FFSSP_HVMS.txt B280_FFSSP.raw B280_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B280_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS B280.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (B280.zip) - rename B280.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B280_rawseadas.zip	18/04/07	
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B280_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B280_rawseadas.zip	18/04/07	Binary data transfer Seadas data only at this stage


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08:51:49.51 --- - - - -
08:51:49.51 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:51:49.51 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:51:49.51 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B280
08:51:49.51 --- - - - -
08:52:03.78 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
08:52:12.40 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
08:52:19.10 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
08:52:52.61 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:52.61 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:52.61 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:53:10.67 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 250ms.
08:53:14.88 SWS - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 250ms.
08:53:19.60 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:53:24.92 USH - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 250ms.
08:53:36.37 LSH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 250ms.
08:53:39.88 LSH - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 250ms.
08:53:45.98 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:53:46.02 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:53:46.02 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:53:48.92 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:53:49.16 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:53:49.34 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:53:53.56 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:53:57.67 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:54:04.35 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:54:07.56 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:54:10.75 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:55:00.97 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:55:10.12 SWS - - - - Idling
08:55:13.60 LSH - - - - Idling
08:55:15.98 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:55:18.93 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:55:23.00 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:55:28.01 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:56:02.50 USH - - - - Idling
08:56:06.40 LSH - - - - Idling
08:59:21.22 SWS - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
08:59:27.14 SWS - 500 - - Sample period changed from 1000ms to 500ms.
09:06:23.75 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
09:13:17.99 SWS - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:13:20.74 SWS - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:13:26.62 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:13:26.63 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:13:34.66 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:14:01.74 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:14:01.93 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:14:02.17 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:02.41 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:02.72 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:14:09.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:14:09.90 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:14:10.10 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:10.35 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:13.16 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:23.59 LSH - - - - Idling
09:14:26.47 USH - - - - Idling
09:14:28.71 SWS - - - - Idling
09:14:33.60 USH - - - - Instrument closed.
09:14:37.12 LSH - - - - Instrument closed.
09:14:43.89 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:14:49.74 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:15:25.05 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:25.06 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:25.07 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:53.68 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:15:58.62 USH - - - - Idling

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09:15:59.85 LSH - - - - Idling
09:16:01.48 SWS - - - - Idling
09:16:03.69 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:16:07.18 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:16:11.48 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:16:21.92 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:16:31.04 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:16:34.98 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:18:12.19 --- - - - -
09:18:12.19 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:18:12.19 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:18:12.19 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B280
09:18:12.19 --- - - - -
09:18:22.61 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:18:23.46 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:18:24.36 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:19:02.11 SWS - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:19:05.90 SWS - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:19:09.47 USH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 0ms.
09:19:12.61 USH - - - 0 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 0ms.
09:19:15.67 LSH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 0ms.
09:19:18.78 LSH - - - 0 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 0ms.
09:19:22.57 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:19:22.57 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:19:22.58 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:21:25.60 --- - - - -
09:21:25.60 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:21:25.60 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:21:25.60 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B280
09:21:25.60 --- - - - -
09:21:42.17 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:21:54.23 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:21:56.61 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
09:22:12.44 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:22:15.86 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:22:19.03 USH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
09:22:21.94 USH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:22:26.00 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
09:22:28.73 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:22:31.29 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:22:31.29 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:22:31.30 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:22:43.97 SWS - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
09:22:47.22 SWS - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 1000ms.
09:23:56.02 USH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 1000ms.
09:24:39.45 LSH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
09:24:44.56 LSH - - - 0 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
09:24:50.78 LSH - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:24:55.39 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:27:53.47 USH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
09:27:59.31 USH - - - 0 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
09:28:04.40 LSH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
09:28:09.41 LSH - - - 0 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
09:28:52.76 USH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:28:56.19 USH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:29:04.09 USH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
09:29:14.13 USH - - 0 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
09:29:18.86 USH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:29:21.82 USH - 500 - - Sample period changed from 1000ms to 500ms.
09:29:27.43 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:29:30.64 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
09:29:44.04 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:29:54.47 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:29:59.08 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:30:06.95 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:30:17.39 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:30:22.04 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.

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09:30:32.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:38.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:48.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:31:09.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:31:11.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:31:12.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:39:42.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:42.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:42.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:50.21	USH	-	-	0	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
10:40:21.54	USH	-	-	1000	-	VIS int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
10:42:35.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:42:37.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:42:37.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:30.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:30.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:30.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:48.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** take off
12:02:57.76	USH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 500ms.
12:03:04.21	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
12:03:07.79	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
12:03:12.78	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
12:06:00.03	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 300ms.
12:06:13.73	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
12:06:17.57	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 75ms.
12:06:21.51	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
12:06:26.45	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:06:31.44	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 75ms.
12:06:36.97	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
12:06:43.73	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
12:15:57.00	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:17:36.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** functionality testing - ignore data TFN
12:17:39.57	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:17:41.60	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:17:43.57	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:17:45.46	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:17:46.85	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:17:47.86	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:19:01.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** testing finished
12:19:56.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** looking down at cloud
12:20:08.59	LSH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
12:20:21.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:21.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:21.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:22.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:22.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:32.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:52.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** ignore last darks - rubbish
12:21:04.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:21:09.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:21:16.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:17.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:23.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:24.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:28.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:39.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:44.28	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 500ms.
12:22:06.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:06.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:06.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:08.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:08.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:12.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:27.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** better darks laast time
12:31:44.85	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 350ms.
12:31:50.95	LSH	-	-	-	1000	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
12:31:56.10	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
12:32:02.26	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 250ms.
12:32:06.24	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.

```

12:32:30.04 --- - - - - *** flying through cloud
12:34:00.86 --- - - - - *** sc layer below
12:37:07.46 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:37:07.48 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:37:07.82 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:37:08.84 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:37:12.89 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:37:18.29 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:37:29.35 --- - - - - *** good darks
12:38:20.07 --- - - - - *** start r1 12 37 37
12:38:39.01 --- - - - - *** @ 1400ft
12:44:09.52 LSH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
12:44:41.22 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
12:53:34.07 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
12:53:37.85 SWS - - - 350 NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 350ms.
12:53:43.49 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
12:53:53.50 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:53:53.52 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:53:53.69 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:53:58.96 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:53:59.13 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:54:04.34 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:54:09.50 --- - - - - *** good dark
12:57:50.93 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
12:57:59.14 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:58:16.71 --- - - - - *** start R2 @ 1000ft
13:02:43.45 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
13:02:47.87 LSH - - - 0 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 0ms.
13:02:52.43 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 0ms to 1000ms.
13:09:17.68 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
13:09:20.94 SWS - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
13:09:29.67 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:29.71 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:29.86 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:34.12 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:35.31 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:40.52 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:42.76 --- - - - - *** good dark
13:24:55.66 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
13:24:58.88 SWS - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
13:26:13.26 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:13.44 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:13.64 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:16.60 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:18.89 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:23.72 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:26.25 --- - - - - *** good dark
13:29:07.26 --- - - - - *** scan head mobility tests - ignore data TFN
13:31:02.44 --- - - - - *** tests ended
13:46:59.88 --- - - - - *** trying 10Deg scans starting from 20F
13:47:08.09 --- - - - - *** 20F
13:47:15.55 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
13:47:19.76 SWS - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
13:47:23.32 SWS - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
13:47:34.12 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
13:47:38.95 SWS - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 1000ms.
13:49:06.49 --- - - - - *** 10F
13:50:17.79 --- - - - - *** 0F
13:51:10.88 --- - - - - *** 10A
13:52:07.93 --- - - - - *** 20A
13:52:15.11 SWS - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
13:53:11.91 --- - - - - *** 30A
13:53:44.23 --- - - - - *** 40A
13:54:10.94 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
13:54:27.63 --- - - - - *** 50A
13:54:38.22 SWS - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 750ms.
13:54:42.30 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
13:55:32.62 --- - - - - *** 60A
13:56:38.70 --- - - - - *** descending to 50ft

```

13:59:11.68	---	-	-	-	*** 70A
13:59:11.77	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:59:22.82	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
14:06:53.96	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:07:00.72	SWS	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
14:07:04.02	SWS	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
14:07:11.88	LSH	-	-	400	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
14:08:11.03	SWS	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 350ms.
14:08:14.17	SWS	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
14:08:18.39	SWS	-	-	1000	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 1000ms.
14:08:30.93	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:31.03	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:31.23	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:36.36	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:41.56	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:41.77	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:44.17	---	-	-	-	*** good dark
14:21:00.93	LSH	-	-	750	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
14:21:09.22	USH	-	-	1000	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
14:21:19.91	LSH	-	-	1000	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 1000ms.
14:21:46.87	---	-	-	-	*** NADIR view
14:29:54.41	---	-	-	-	*** OAT -50C
14:29:59.20	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:59.27	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:59.37	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:09.67	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:09.84	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:10.04	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:12.31	---	-	-	-	*** good dark
14:34:24.92	---	-	-	-	*** starting down sun run @ FL300
14:35:24.14	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 150F
14:35:39.21	SWS	-	-	250	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
14:36:16.44	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 140
14:36:31.05	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 160F
14:37:28.51	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 170F
14:38:21.19	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 180
14:39:12.97	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 174Aft NADIR view
14:39:35.14	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 170Aft
14:39:36.81	LSH	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 500ms.
14:39:42.24	LSH	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
14:40:45.44	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 160Aft
14:41:54.64	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 15Aft
14:42:03.69	---	-	-	-	*** 150AFT
14:42:49.26	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 100Aft
14:43:00.67	SWS	-	-	15	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 15ms.
14:43:05.03	SWS	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
14:43:10.71	SWS	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
14:43:47.69	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 90 AFT looking back at sun
14:43:52.81	SWS	-	-	15	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
14:44:36.85	---	-	-	-	*** contrailing
14:45:08.34	---	-	-	-	*** end of down sun run
14:45:12.25	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:45:44.24	---	-	-	-	*** across sun run
14:45:53.85	SWS	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 350ms.
14:45:57.02	SWS	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 750ms.
14:46:00.81	SWS	-	-	1000	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 1000ms.
14:46:33.65	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 160F
14:47:15.50	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 170F
14:47:34.00	---	-	-	-	*** aircraft heading 320deg
14:47:56.37	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 174A
14:48:37.56	---	-	-	-	*** OAT -53, scan head still easy to move.
14:48:49.54	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 160A
14:49:37.74	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 150A
14:50:49.75	---	-	-	-	*** end across run sun
14:50:58.25	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:52:02.85	---	-	-	-	*** into sun run
14:52:18.36	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 150Aft
14:52:42.76	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 160A
14:53:36.16	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 170A

14:54:09.51	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 180
14:54:43.07	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 170F
14:54:52.12	USH	-	-	200	- VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
14:54:57.47	LSH	-	-	350	- VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 350ms.
14:55:14.61	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 160F
14:55:46.71	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 150F
14:55:59.82	SWS	-	-	300	- VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
14:56:05.22	SWS	-	-	200	- VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
14:56:24.56	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 140F
14:56:34.87	SWS	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 750ms.
14:56:38.36	SWS	-	-	100	- VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
14:56:54.99	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 130F
14:57:06.62	SWS	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
14:57:12.96	SWS	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
14:57:29.97	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 120F
14:57:39.87	SWS	-	-	15	- VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 15ms.
14:57:43.85	SWS	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
14:58:03.37	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 110F
14:58:13.04	SWS	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
14:58:43.18	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 100F
14:59:52.71	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 90F. a/c pitch angle 5.6deg
15:00:45.43	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 100f
15:01:25.15	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 110F
15:01:38.79	---	-	-	-	*** end into sun run
15:02:16.65	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:02:51.41	---	-	-	-	*** start across sun run
15:02:59.69	SWS	-	-	350	- VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 350ms.
15:03:03.41	SWS	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 750ms.
15:03:09.61	SWS	-	-	1000	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 1000ms.
15:04:18.08	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 140A
15:04:26.92	SWS	-	-	300	- VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
15:05:01.94	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 150A
15:05:24.47	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 160A
15:05:32.68	SWS	-	-	200	- VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
15:05:52.21	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 170A
15:06:24.25	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 180
15:07:11.13	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 170F
15:07:37.89	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 160F
15:07:53.65	---	-	-	-	*** end across sun run
15:08:31.14	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:11:14.91	SWS	-	-	300	- VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
15:11:34.93	---	-	-	-	*** FL320 starting down sun run
15:11:53.44	---	-	-	-	*** NADIR view
15:12:15.35	SWS	-	-	400	- VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
15:12:25.22	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:25.22	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:25.32	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:35.66	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:12:35.86	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:12:36.10	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:12:38.10	---	-	-	-	*** good dark
15:13:07.65	SWS	-	-	200	- VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
15:15:35.53	SWS	-	-	350	- VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
15:17:55.51	USH	-	-	250	- VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
15:18:03.24	LSH	-	-	400	- VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
15:21:27.48	---	-	-	-	*** end run
15:22:24.27	---	-	-	-	*** in turn
15:22:35.08	---	-	-	-	*** start across sun run
15:23:34.29	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:34.55	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:34.87	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:44.71	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:44.98	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:45.30	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:47.25	---	-	-	-	*** good dark
15:27:55.55	---	-	-	-	*** end run
15:28:01.42	---	-	-	-	*** turning
15:28:56.84	---	-	-	-	*** into sun run
15:40:03.05	---	-	-	-	*** end run + turning

```

15:41:35.96 --- - - - - *** start last across sun run
15:44:01.51 --- - - - - *** still on NADIR view
15:45:11.64 --- - - - - *** end run and start profile down to fl200
15:46:17.08 SWS - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 150ms.
15:46:20.86 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 750ms.
15:53:24.44 SWS - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
15:53:27.05 SWS - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 1000ms.
15:53:38.80 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
15:53:45.45 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:54:00.97 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 750ms.
15:54:21.35 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:54:21.71 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:54:22.04 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:54:29.29 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:54:32.16 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:54:32.49 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:54:34.42 --- - - - - *** good dark
15:58:06.63 --- - - - - *** end descent and start profile climb to
fl320
16:00:18.04 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
16:00:21.15 SWS - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.
16:00:35.62 LSH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
16:07:41.41 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
16:13:17.74 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
16:13:23.64 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
16:13:26.95 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
16:25:39.77 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
16:25:47.66 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:25:47.87 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:25:48.23 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:25:55.59 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:25:58.31 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:25:58.66 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:26:00.51 --- - - - - *** good dark
16:29:28.17 LSH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
16:31:20.51 SWS - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
16:31:24.94 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:31:34.92 LSH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
16:34:38.38 --- - - - - *** movement tests ignore data TFN
16:38:49.22 --- - - - - *** tests finished
16:38:55.94 --- - - - - *** nadir view
16:49:51.67 --- - - - - *** end science and test
16:49:56.43 LSH - - - - Idling
16:49:59.46 USH - - - - Idling
16:50:01.75 SWS - - - - Idling
16:50:19.67 SWS - - - - Instrument closed.
16:50:25.20 USH - - - - Instrument closed.
16:50:28.96 LSH - - - - Instrument closed.

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ARIES flight log

Flight: B280

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Date: 29-3-7 Operator(s): VANCE Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: ASAS 1AS1 cal/val shake down. (N, Sea)

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
							For earlier pre flight stuff see log book
111328	-	1.cal			71	23	1. Cal = 1x60, H; 1x60, C
11150							power change. Light precip. on pan, t/p climb through cloud.
1206							clearing above.
120700	P1	1.cal		0	71	23	
1213							window shade problem. CDH restart OK
121522	P1	1.cal		0	59.9	22.4	H shroud 38.7
121653				C			H Shroud & Centre climbing slowly. Shroud quickly catches base
121830	Transit			C	70	22	T _{amb.} = -16°C
1220							Cold target reset to +10°C, shutter opened
122350	P2↓?	-	-	0	70	19	HBB sh 60° - CBB back to +20
							Some Ci overhead - not sure if we can see it Realtime T _b has general baseline slope anyway
1237	R1	1400 1400					
124128		1400					Archie CDH stopped to insert new script
1245		1400					CDH restarted. OK.
124640	R1	1400 1.cal		C	71	22	in SCA Top?
125052	R1	2. 23		0	70	22	2. 23 = 3min Z, gains = 4, 16.
1255	R1	1. Cal		C	71	23	above script didn't put gains back on mirror
1256	ERISP4						Much haze.
125748	R3, 1000	2. 23		0	70	23	trying, again. NCT saturating
130700		2. 23		0	67	26	aborted
1310							CDH restarted to pick up script change.
1315	1000	2. 2					initial mirror, gain requests are read OK but ones after sleep are random. Best talk to Bonem.
		"					
		"					
131656		"			67	29	
132105	1000	1. Cal		0	65	28	T: +7°C
132547	"	1. cal		0	71	28	Z script removed from config.

— M —

ARIES flight log

Flight: B280

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Date: 29-3-7

Operator(s): VANCE

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: /ASI cal/Val shakedown N. Sea.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
143108	EP	1. Cal	C	71	22	FL300	
143242	turn	1. Cal	C	71	21		
143405		360x1	Z	0	71	22	Odd O ₃ band. TWT! Should be!
143714	R3			0			
143843		360x1	Z	0	70	22	O ₃ warmer than windows
144147		1. Cal	O	70	23	HBB shroud 51.2	
144320?	R3.1	180x1	Z	0	70	22	aborted at ER3
144440	turn	1. Cal	O	69	22		
144615	R3.2	360x1	Z	0	69	22	gains 2, 8. Nasty window region PIC
144925				0			shutter closed
145000	R3.2	1. Cal	C	70.5	21.7		
1453		1. Cal	C	70.5	22	INSB gains all 8!	
1455	R3.3	600x1		C	70.5	22	
15000		1. Cal	C	71	21	oven Cu clean above	
150428		360x1	Z	0	70	22	Sub-visual Ci? PIC
150830		1. Cal	C	71	22	gap before cal w' shutter closed	
151120		1. Cal	C	71	23	gains now 2, 2.	
151300		360x1	Z	0	70	22	PIC
151601		360x1	Z	0	71	22	odd MCT spectrum
152020	ER4.1			C			
152125	turn	1. Cal	C	70	22		
152352	R4.2	360x1	N	C	71	22	Much haze below, some Cu(?)
152607	"	1. Cal	C	71	22		
152720	ER4.2			0			
152754	turn	1. Cal	O	69.5	23	looks clean as a bell above but	
152911	R4.3	360x1	N	O	64	22	
153320	"	1. Cal	O	53	22	Hmm.	
1534				C		still horizon looks very	
153617		1. Cal	C	70	22	hazy (& surface) clean above	
153727		120x1	N	C	71	22	passing some Cu at end.
153848	Turn	1. Cal	C	70	22		

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	29/03/07	Flight	B280	log pages
Operator(s)	Campaign				
Departure	Arrival				

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection					•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers					•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers					•
FERA on			at time		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18 °C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20 40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time		
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers					
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software			at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual	
Weather	Cloud	8/8 cloud	Precip	occasional	
	Surface		Pressure		
	Other				

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	08:50:00	
Brightness temps 'sensible'				•	
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	345	Cold	281
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)
	41	32	38	39	42

Power changeover

Headset on before start		•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		•
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	•
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B280**.....

 Date 29/3/07.....

 Operator's name: D.T./S.B......

 Page 1 of

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water} current	Remarks
12:23:00	P2?	FL110	10			↓ 25	10	PROBLEMS DOWN TO SOFT FROM TRAV - INLET HTR OFF
12:39	R1	FL1500	13.9	45%	80%	↓ 5	34	SURPRISE RUN. 15min
12:47		"						PRE HTR ON
								NOTE: SCALE ON SCATTER VS RH ALL ZONES CHILLER KEEPS LOCKING UP.
12:58	R2	1000	13.7	38%	37%	↑ 25	5	NOTE: TIME DISCREPANCY IN CHARTS S → 1min Behind
?						↑ 40		PC CLOCK
13:16	"	1000	14.4	30%	85%	↓ 10	40	
13:23	"	1000	14.4	29%	50%	↑ 35	20	
13:26	"	"	14.1	32%	74%	↑ 40	35	
13:28	"	1000	14.2	33%	83%	↑ 45	40	NOT MUCH GROWTH SEEN
13:34	"	1000	16.4	32%	94%	↓ 35	45	(@ 94% ← WET DRY GRAPH SAME
13:39	"	1000	16.6	37%	72%	↓ 25	35	
13:43	"	"	"	37%	61%	↑ 35	25	
13:46	"	"	"	32%	72%	↑ 40	35	SOME GROWTH SPOTTED
14:06	P6					↓ 43	45	NOTE CANT SEE ANYTHING ON W:D GRAPH generally.

MISSED A CHANCE TO 45

Folder Content

1L5520 → 13:07. 3.8 GB DATA → 3.81 GB

RAW

RAW

In Flight log 20070329.txt

ACTi

User : Root
Default (Administrator) Account: Admin (Capital A)
Password: 123456

FAAM LAPTOP 4

ACTi software on laptop 4 set to record from before power changeover on ground.

FFC from start to low level flying.
DFC from 130520 - 1000' to end of run then down to 50' (135804) and profile up to rear 140757 Contrails* from about 14:26 on

3Mbps 16:20 40ish (contained from Channel1_20070329_172006_898.raw on on FAAM Laptop 3). Higher bitrate doesn't appear to increase image quality very much.

* Brightness default of 50% not showing very good image from RFC so adjusted it using IE ACXti Video Adjustment settings to 42 the 31% around 14:30 for better image

Brightness/Contrast etc can be changed from both ACTi web configurator (doesn't stop recording) AND FROM ACTi STREAMING ACTIVATOR (WHICH DOES STOP RECORDING. CHANGING VIEWS AT 3Mbps FROM 1-UP TO 4-UP HAD THE SYSTEM NOT RESPOND FOR OVER A MINUTE around 16:38ish. Check whether data was still being recorded. Video stopped around them by trying to alter contrast.

ACTi web interface alters contrast for all recorders of a camera while ACTi STREAMING ACTIVATOR on different PCs changes it just for the stream to that PC.

FAAM LAPTOP 3

Viewing the ACTi admin webpage (http://192.168.101.100/cgi-bin/videoconfiguration.cgi) the video didn't display but the following message did "Click here to install the following ActiveX control: 'MCTRLMEDIA.dll' from 'ACTi Corporation'..." After clicking to install the video showed up on screen. This may be what is required for Windows Media Player. to work.

Windows Media Player displays recorded image files after installing ffdshow-20040329.exe from ACTi CD (shows up as ffdshow MPEG-4 Video Decoder codec post install)

Post take off tried installing Milestone XProtect which went fine. Setting up the video server didn't go as well and stalled at the Device Setup Wizard when asking for "the video device's administrator account (called 'root' or 'admin' on some devices)." The default option of Autodetect didn't work and neither did the ACTi and ACTi 2300Q options. No other ACTi options were offered.

Autodetect Device produced "The system was unable to autodetect the device. Please specify a device type." error message.

ACTi produced "The system was unable to detect the selected device type. Please check that the device is connected properly, and that the IP address, ports, password and selected device type is entered correctly."

ACTi 2300Q produces the same error message as ACTi above.

Ping and web browser both can see the device so something within the Milestone XProtect software/settings must be the problem.

```
C:\>ping 192.168.101.100
Pinging 192.168.101.100 with 32 bytes of data:
Reply from 192.168.101.100: bytes=32 time<1ms TTL=255
```

Back to the previous screen and clicked on the Port setup option.

Default port settings are HTTP port 80 and FTP port 21. Looking at the ACTi web configurator settings via IE the HTTP port is 80 and there is no specific mention of an FTP port. There are two Search Server ports so I tried each of those
Search Server Port 1 6005
Search Server Port 2 6006

I didn't want to change the ports on the acti (TO 21 AS A TEST) in case it interrupted the recording. Post install the network connection seems to have stopped.

Changing to 6005 and 6006 gave the same error messages as before.

Could it be that the Username (no option is given to change it from whatever defaults the software attempts to use) doesn't try the option with a capital "A" which is what the IE login screen requires rather than "a"? The option is there to change the root Account name in the ACTi options via IE but again I didn't want to try this while recording in flight.

There is no option to change the Subnet mask either (255.255.255.0 on the aircraft network) which could be a possible problem.

GARDEM 01273608331

AIR-GRAFT NETWORK SETTINGS WINDP 4

IP ADDRESS 192.168.101.101
SUBNET 255.255.255.0

? PREFER DNS? 212.30.200.199
? ? 212.30.200.200

DEVICE PREFIX MILESTONE WMA
SUPPORT

MILESTONE SAFARI REPLY — FEB 15TH
DEVICE PREFIX

Flight:

B280

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 04/09/2007
14:22:26

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

29/03/2007 19:02:17

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B280

Date: 29 March 2007

Instruments

1. 30 cc noise in Ch. 1 of PCASP
2. Satcom option on Horace does not work consistently
3. FM Keyboard has problems
4. Position reports not being sent
5. Optical disk stopped recording data for a maximum of 38 mins
6. Turbulence probe drop out between 15:52:30 and 15:53:45, instrument regained composure!

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B280:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
TDLAS	No log taken
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	18 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

- 1 x Forward Facing Cameras
- 1 x For/Rear/Upward Facing Cameras
- 1 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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